

Enhancing Dielectric and Flexural Properties of Glass Fiber Composites via Vacuum Pressure Impregnation

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Abstract:

This research focuses on examining the capabilities of VPI in improving the mechanical and dielectric characteristic of glass fiber composites. Thus, vacuum and pressure used in VPI enhance resin infiltration within the fibre structures minimizing the void volume thus enhancing the performance of the composites. This work shows that when the VPI process is applied on glass fibre composites with epoxy polymer, then dielectrics strength of 15. About 12 kV/mm and the flexural bending stress was established to be 489.33 MPa. Statistical was performed using Analysis of variance (ANOVA) which revealed that the performances of all the properties were significantly improved due to the implementation of VPI. From the results of this study, it is seen that VPI is efficient for creation of new composites possessing enhanced dielectric characteristics, which allows the non-destructive application of high voltage circuit breakers in electro engineering. The findings have provided important findings necessary for achieving best microstructures that have enhanced the construction of advanced composite materials hence enriching the subject of composite material science.

Keywords: ANOVA, Composite Materials, Dielectric Strength, Flexural Bending Stress, Glass Fiber, Polymer material

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1. Introduction

There has been a progressive increase in adaption of composite materials in electrical applications thus enhancing growth of efficient composites. Of these, glass fibre composite material has emerged as the most preferred one because of its mechanical and dielectric performances [1]. These properties make them suitable to be used in the applications such as high voltage electrical circuit breakers and insulation systems [2]. Nevertheless, it should be noted that the record of glass fibre composites is highly sensitive to the degree of the resin infiltration, which is often difficult due to the factory porosity and the requirement for deep resin penetration in order to minimize the presence of voids [3].

The Vacuum Pressure Impregnation (VPI) process has been proven distinctive as being the most effective process for the improvement of the quality of resin impregnation in composite materials. When vacuum and pressure are applied the cycles in VPI process enables the resin to properly penetrate through the fibers thus reducing void sizes thus enhancing the performance of the composite [4]. However, the crucial factor of the VPI process, which is controlling the parameters like the curing temperature, number of layers, curing time etc, continues to be a significant factor in achieving the desirable mechanical and dielectric characteristic [5].

The objective of the present work is to determine the process parameter of VPI for improving the flexural and dielectric

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strength of the glass fiber composite. Thus, the authors of the study expose those parameters and study their effects on the characteristics of the composite material examining the optimal conditions for achieving the best material characteristics. The novel dielectric strength testing setup designed for this work gives accurate and reproducible results that augment the current understanding of the process and its result [6].

Glass fiber composites have found their way into several applications in engineering due to their good strength to weight ratio, corrosion resistance and design versatility. Nonetheless, the presence of porous in the types of composites especially from imperfect impregnation of resins used during production may pose a major problem to the efficiency of the materials by altering both its mechanical and dielectric characteristics. Vacuum Pressure Impregnation has been shown to be a very efficient technique to overcome this challenge [4].

This research focuses on the effects of the VPI process variables on the mechanical and electrical properties, specifically, the flexural and dielectric strength of glass fiber composites. In a structured experimental design utilizing Analysis of Variance, it is planned to determine the conditions that result in the material characteristics of superior quality. Epoxy based Glass fiber reinforced plastic composites are the main subject of investigation; the goal established for the study is to achieve a dielectric strength of 15. 12 kV/mm & a flexural bending stress of 489. 33 MPa. The present work raises the knowledge of VPI optimization as a prerequisite to create efficient composites for challenging requests, including high-voltage circuit breakers in electrical engineering [7].

This allows for enhancing the overall comprehension of what the process conditions should be for the production of materials with superior characteristics, helping in the advancement of more capable composite materials.

2. Methods and Methodology

2.1 Materials

Epoxy Resin: There was a regular epoxy resin system employed that involved epoxy resin and hardener in the appropriate proportions as recommended by the manufacturer of the epoxy system. The reason for the selection of the resin was due to its applicability in glass fibers and the accomplishment of high mechanical & dielectric characteristics [8].

Glass Fibers: E-glass fibers were chosen for high tensile strength and durability of the material. The fibers were received in cloth mat form with stipulated thickness and density of the fibers to be used [9].

2.2 Vacuum Pressure Impregnation Process

The study aims to investigate the optimal conditions for enhancing the mechanical and dielectric properties of glass fiber composites through the Vacuum Pressure Impregnation (VPI) process. The specific objectives are to determine the effects of varying the preparation steps, layup configuration, vacuum, and pressure levels on the final composite properties.

- i. Preparation: Describe the measures followed in the preparation of the glass fiber fabric and epoxy resin system. This can reach from preheated of the fabric, degassing of the resin, or from cutting the fabric to the needed size
- ii. Layup: Explain how the glass fiber fabric was placed in the mold, how many plies of fabric was used, and the directions of those plies.
- iii. Vacuum Bagging: Enumerate the proper setup of a vacuum bagging setup such as the type of bagging film that is used, the type of sealant tape, where the vacuum ports are located, and the manner on which the resin inlet and outlet are laid.

Impregnation Cycle: Give a breakdown of the VPI cycle used with a view to be noting.

Vacuum Stage: Define the vacuum level that has been applied and also determine the time that the vacuum hold has been set at.

Pressure Stage: It is, therefore, necessary to state the pressure level that has been applied together with the time duration during which pressure has been applied.

Cure Cycle: Describe how the cure cycle temperature and duration of the cure cycle, and whether there was any temperature ramp and/or holding periods.

Figure 1- Vacuum Moulding process

Demolding: Describe on how cured composite was retrieved from the mould. [10]

2.3 Methods for evaluation of dielectric strength

a) Dielectric Strength

The setup was designed to check the axial dielectric strength of the composite material. It consists of extension housing, bushing, Electrode, Tank cover and NRV (Non return valve). The NRV was using to fill the dielectric gas inside the extension housing. The test specimen will be placed inside the two electrodes. With the help of spring and spring guide the sufficient pressure was applied on the specimen to hold the electrode during the voltage application. The electrode was made of Aluminium alloy material with proper radiuses to withstand the dielectric stresses generated during the test.

The complete the dielectric test setup was placed on voltage generator to apply the voltage across the electrodes. The voltage is applied between the electrodes in step manner and put for the 1min. voltage withstand. After that the voltage will be increased and check for the breakdown voltage. The dielectric strength will calculate by dividing the breakdown voltage to distance between the two electrodes.

Figure 2 - Dielectric Strength testing setup

b) Sample Test Specimen for Dielectric Testing

The sample test specimen used for dielectric testing was a cylindrical tube with an outer diameter of 36 mm, an inner diameter of 24 mm, and a length of 100 mm.

Figure 3- Dielectric Strength Tested sample

2.4 Methods for evaluation of flexural strength

a) Three point bending test

The beam is a tube specimen and is propped near to its both ends. In the three-point bending the beam is loaded at the mid-point of the span. Due to the two end supports and one center load application in the mid of the beam span this method is called three point bending [10].

Figure 4 - Three point bending test on sample

In this test a specimen with tube section is placed on two parallel supporting pins in such a way that there is a gap between them. In order to apply the loading force, loading jaws are provided and they are incorporated at the centre. The supporting pin and loading jaws are provided on the fixture

so as to enable them to pivot freely in a plane perpendicular to the pin axis and to the specimen axis.

b) Sample Test Specimen for flexural strength

ASTM Standard: The testing procedure followed the ASTM D790-17 standard, which outlines the test methods for flexural properties of unreinforced and reinforced plastics and electrical insulating materials.

The sample test specimen used for flexural strength testing was a cylindrical tube with an outer diameter of 36mm, an inner d

Figure 5- Flexural Strength Tested sample

3. Results & Discussions

Minitab statistical software have been used for this purpose. Models have been made of the modulus strength and dielectric strength. ANOVA has been used to find out how each parameter affects the modulus strength, dielectric strength and a linear regression model has been made to predict output model regression model has been made to predict output model [11].

3.1 Calculation of SN ratio

SN ration is used to normalize the experimental data in specific range calculated and the response for SN ratio smaller is better selected.

Given below is the equation of Signal-Noise (S/N) ratio for the response

$$S/N = -10\log_{10}\sum \frac{y^2}{n}$$

Where y is the response value and n is the number of total experiments.

Similarly, Signal to Noise ratio values can be obtained for other experimental runs in orthogonal. The Cumulative data for S/N ratio glass fibre epoxy resins composite of modulus strength, dielectric strength are calculated as shown in table 1.

Table 1 - L9 Signal to Noise Ratio of Flexural Bending Stress, dielectric strength

Experiments	Inputs Factors			Mechanical properties		Dielectric properties	
	Curing temperature (°C)	Number of layers (No's)	Curing time (minute)	Flexural Bending Stress (MPa)	S/N Ratio	Dielectric Strength (Kv/mm)	S/N Ratio
Sample 1	110	4	30	418.11	52.4258	12.34	21.8263
Sample 2	110	5	40	468.68	53.4175	11.98	21.5691
Sample 3	110	6	50	412.80	52.3148	15.02	23.5334
Sample 4	120	4	40	478.60	53.5995	12.12	21.6701
Sample 5	120	5	50	462.55	53.3032	14.36	23.1431
Sample 6	120	6	30	423.89	52.5451	14.89	23.4579
Sample 7	130	4	50	441.78	52.9041	13.79	22.7913
Sample 8	130	5	30	458.57	53.2281	14.18	23.0335
Sample 9	130	6	40	456.53	53.1894	14.50	23.2274

With the help of the Minitab 19 software, the values of the S/N ratio are found. All of the experiments show that there isn't much difference in the S/N ratio.

a. Main Effects Flexural Bending Stress and Dielectric Strength

Graph 1 shows the main effects plot from S/N ratios. High S/N ratio: Indicates that the signal is much stronger than the noise. A high SNR is generally desired as it means that the quality of the signal is good and less likely to be distorted by noise. Low S/N ratio: Indicates that the signal is weaker compared to the noise. A low S/N ratio means that the noise is more prominent and can obscure or distort the signal.

Graph A: Main Effects Plot for flexural bending stress

Graph B: Main Effects Plot for dielectric strength

From Graph 1, the Main Effect plot for the S/N ratio of glass fibre polymer composite for flexural bending stress optimally measured response is the level of a factor that has the highest SN ratio. The optimal flexural bending stress parameters were 120 °C curing temperature (level 2), 5 number of layer (level 2) and 40 min curing time (level 2).

From Graph 2, the Main Effect plot for the S/N ratio of glass fibre polymer composite for dielectric strength optimally measured response is the level of a factor that has the highest SN ratio. The optimal flexural bending stress parameters were 130 °C curing temperature (level 3), 6 number of layer (level 3) and 50 min curing time (level 3).

3.3 Analysis of Variance

ANOVA is a statistical method for figuring out how well a number of different variables fit together. With a confidence level of 95%, or P values of less than 0.05, the results were

found. It also shows how much each element contributed and how much it changed, which shows which factor had the biggest effect on the result [13]

$fLN = N-1$ gives the number of degrees of freedom as a whole.

Here's how to figure out degrees of freedom for residual error:

$DF = (fLN) - (\text{Sum of DF of all the terms included in the model})$

In this study, a standard L9 array with three levels and four parameters is used. In this study, the winding angle, the number of layers, the winding speed are the three process parameters those were chosen [14]

Total fLN degrees = $N-1 = 9-1 = 8$

Each parameter has three levels, which means it has two degrees of freedom.

DF for residual error = $8-(2+2+2+2) = 0$ [15]

Table 2 - ANNOVA Result for flexural bending stress

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value	Contribution %
Curing temperature	2	848.05	424.02	18.37	0.050	18.84
Number of layers	2	1556.64	778.32	33.73	0.029	34.58
Curing time	2	2049.57	1024.79	44.41	0.022	45.54
Residual Error	2	46.15	23.08			
Total	8	4500.42				

The table shows the ANOVA for glass fibre polymer composite material. The table shows that the Curing temperature (18.84%), Number of layers (34.58%), and Curing time (45.54%) have a significant impact on flexural bending stress.

The ANOVA results indicate that all three independent variables (Curing temperature, Number of Layers, and Curing time) significantly influence the flexural bending stress.

Curing time contributes the most to explaining the variation in flexural bending stress, followed closely by Number of Layers and then Curing temperature.

Graph 3 - Contribution of process parameter for flexural bending stress

Table 3 - Model summary

S	R-Sq	R-Sq(adj)
0.0803	98.97%	95.90%

S: Standard error of the estimate is 0.0803, indicating a small average deviation of predicted values from actual values.

R-Sq (R-Squared): Coefficient of determination is 98.97% indicates high predictability of the dependent variable from the independent variables.

R-Sq(adj) (Adjusted R-Squared): Adjusted coefficient of determination is 95.90% indicates the adjusted predictability considering the number of predictors in the model.

Source	DF	Adj SS	Adj MS	F-Value	P-Value	Contribution %
Curing temperature	2	0.76891	0.38446	21.62	0.044	15.48
Number of layers	2	2.63269	1.31634	74.02	0.013	53.01
Curing time	2	1.52853	0.76427	42.98	0.023	30.77
Residual Error	2	0.03557	0.01778			
Total	8	4.96570				

The table shows the ANOVA for glass fibre polymer composite material. The table shows that the Curing temperature (15.48 %), Number of layers (53.01%), and curing time (30.77%) have a significant impact on dielectric strength.

Graph 3 - Contribution of process parameter for flexural bending stress

Table 5 - Model summary

S	R-Sq	R-Sq(adj)
0.0687	99.28%	97.13%

3.4 Development of Regression Model

Minitab is utilized to create a regression model. By substituting the experimental values of the parameters into the regression equation, flexural bending stress and dielectric strength values for all levels of study parameters can be predicted. The correlation between predicted and experimental values of flexural bending stress and dielectric strength is also demonstrated via graphical representation [15]. Using design Minitab software, a mathematical model for winding angle, number of layer and winding speed is calculated and regression analysis is performed to obtain the predicted value of flexural bending stress and dielectric strength

a. Regression Equation for flexural bending stress

$$\text{Flexural Bending Stress} = 359 + 0.95 [\text{Curing temperature}] - 7.5 [\text{Number of layers}] + 0.28 [\text{Curing time}]$$

b. Regression Equation for dielectric strength

$$\text{Dielectric Strength} = 1.12 + 0.0522 [\text{Curing temperature}] + 1.027 [\text{Number of layers}] + 0.0293 [\text{Curing time}]$$

Table 6 shows a comparison between the flexural bending stress and dielectric strength measured by three point bending testing and the predicted by a mathematical Regression Equation 1 equation.

Table 6 - Experimental and Predicted Values

Sr. No.	Flexural Bending Stress			Dielectric Strength		
	Experimental value	Predicted value	Error %	Experimental value	Predicted value	Error %
1	418.11	441.90	5.38	12.34	11.84	4.22
2	468.68	437.20	7.20	11.98	13.16	4.98
3	412.80	432.50	4.56	15.02	14.48	3.73
4	478.60	454.20	5.37	12.12	12.66	4.26
5	462.55	449.50	2.90	14.36	13.98	2.72
6	423.89	436.40	2.87	14.89	14.42	3.25
7	441.78	466.50	5.30	13.79	13.47	2.37
8	458.57	453.40	1.14	14.18	13.92	1.87
9	456.53	448.70	1.74	14.50	15.24	4.86

The difference between the calculated values for flexural bending stress and dielectric strength and the experimental values for each experience was found to be less than 10%. We can therefore say that the regression equation that was made is correct. Graph 3 is a picture of the experimental data and the values those were calculated using the regression equation.

3.5 Confirmation of Experiment Result

The difference between the value of the flexural bending stress and dielectric strength from the confirmation experiment and the value predicted by the regression model.

Table 7 - Confirmation Experiment Result

Parameter	Experimental value	Predicted value	Error %
Flexural Bending Stress, MPa	489.33	480.45	1.84
Dielectric Strength Kv/mm	15.12	15.53	2.64

Keeping the parameters at the best levels suggested by the optimization method, a confirmation experiment was done, and the Flexural Bending Stress and Dielectric Strength was compared to what the regression model predicted while keeping the parameters at the same levels. The difference between the actual result and the one that was predicted is 1.84% and 2.64% resp. This shows that the experimental value and the estimated value are similar.

4. Conclusions

VPI or Vacuum Pressure Impregnation process is one of the effective processes in order to increase mechanical and dielectric properties of Glass fiber composite.

This study systematically manipulated some of the curing conditions such as temperature, number of layers, and curing time to enhance the characteristics of the composite.

The capabilities of the given VPI process for the manufacturing of composites for high voltage circuit breaker applications are well illustrated by these observations.

The ANOVA test which was used in analyzing the data showed that the dyed strength attributed by the number of layers used had the highest variance of 53%. This shows that subject and area of manufacture had the least mean response of 01%, mean response for curing time was (30.77%) and for curing temperature was (15.48%).

For flexural bending stress, curing time had the highest coefficient (0.4554), number of layers had the next highest coefficient of (0.3458) while curing temperature obtained a coefficient of (0.1884).

The regression models that were formulated in this study demonstrated high predictiveness of dielectric strength and of flexural bending stress as the experimental measured likewise to the predicted values. Thus, the research offers a detailed insight into the conditions requiring maximization to facilitate the enhancement of the qualities of the resultant composite material, which would be useful in producing more dependable composite systems.

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Thus, it can be stated that the VPI process improves the characteristics of the glass fiber composites to enhance their applicability for electrical applications. The enhancement of process parameters guarantees the development of high mechanical and high dielectric composites to help open for use in various high performance industries.

5. Authors' Contribution

Mr. Satish Bhalerao planned, conducted the experiments, analyzed the data, and has written the first draft of the manuscript. Mr. Tammaraya Bagale is technical supported in machine and process and Dr. M. S. Kadam supervised reviewed and finally approved the manuscript.

6. Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest about the publication of this research paper.

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